

STAFF RECRUITMENT, HIRING PROCEDURES AND SERVICE DELIVERY IN RIVERS STATE TELEVISION

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Abstract: Staff recruitments and hiring procedures are very important aspect of a public organization because, its effects on an organization is felt in the quality of service delivery. This study examined staff recruitment, hiring procedures and service delivery in Rivers State Television (RSTV). The study adopted the Institutional Theory as its theoretical framework. The social survey research design was employed as the method for gathering and analyzing data. The population of the study consisted of 115 staff of the RSTV as furnished from the office of the Director of Administration. Sample size was 89, determined by using the Taro Yamene formula. Major instrument for data collection was a 4-point Likert Scale Questionnaire administered and retrieved from the 89 respondents. Collected data were analyzed using simple percentages while hypothesis was tested by the Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient using T-test. The study found that recruitment practices and hiring procedures have significant effect on the quality of service delivery in Rivers State Television. The study concludes that; the RSTV can attract talented individuals that will advance the quality of service delivery by ensuring and adhering to transparent and comprehensive recruitment and hiring procedures that align with best practices. The study thus, recommends that; recruitment heads should utilize modern, unbiased recruitment techniques that seeks to implement strategic recruitment and hiring procedures which focuses on attracting diverse talents within the purvey of the organization.

Keywords: Recruitment, Hiring, Human Resources, Services, Delivery

Introduction

The academia have devoted a great deal of resources to discussing and documenting the major aspects that define services, especially in public organisations. In spite of these efforts, unifying the field of services has been an enduring challenge (Van Den & Bondarouk, 2017). Service delivery in public organisations is one of the most important aspects that interest the masses and this involves the provision of services to target audience. Thus, public organizations, by virtue of their nature, face distinct challenges and complexities in managing human resources for quality service delivery. Unlike their private counterparts, public entities are often subject to rigorous regulatory frameworks, budget constraints, and heightened public scrutiny. According to Dunner 1964,

as cited in Fatile (2013), public employees are somewhat under great scrutiny to behave suitably within the society. It could be said that the public expects higher standards of ethical behaviour of public employees than other people who are not on the public servants. In the same vein, human resources, often regarded as the lifeblood of any organization, encompass a multifaceted array of elements, including recruitment, training, compensation, performance appraisal, and employee development. In public organizations, especially the Rivers State Broadcasting Corporation, these facets assume heightened importance, given the critical role they play in achieving the organization's objectives while being accountable to the public they serve. Effective human resources management practices are integral in aligning the workforce with organizational goals and in cultivating a culture of productivity, innovation, and accountability. The media is a dynamic instrument for change and reconstruction as well as reformation hence without information no society can function effectively (Okeke, Onyishi, & Ugwu, 2019). Rivers State being as a politically and economically strategic within the South-South subregion of Nigeria needs a well-structured and effective media to reshape and reconstruct its ideologies, living patterns and perception of events and act as checks and balances on the activities of the ruling class. Arguably, the press or mass media in Nigeria is fundamentally partisan as their operations and character of information disseminated often depend on who owns what, the situation or dynamics of the period and the contending interests (Adeleye, Luiz, Muthuri and Amaeshi, 2020). Even with the Government owned media outfits, their operations depend on which ethnic class controls it. Thus, with the proliferation of communication industries separately and/or owned by individuals, groups and different levels of government, clash of interests, crises and conflicts often appear enlarged. Nigerian traditional media sometimes serve as agents and tools of propaganda, war against perceived opponents and veritable instrument for advancing ethnic or tribal course in the pursuit of both personal and assumed tribal agenda (Ajekwe, 2017). Basically, the above have enshrined Nigeria's media production in inefficiency and professional amateurism resulting to mediocre being employed in the name of ethnic nationalism while the bureaucratic principles are almost ignored. The best of Nigerian media production is seen only when justice is skewed against their proprietors (Ogunro, 2014). Outside this, any other thing can be sent out in the name of protecting and advancing the interest of their sponsors. Such pieces of information are characterized by inconsistencies, and ineffectiveness. To address the above, there is every need to examine the human resources architecture and possible problems that have bedeviled the government owned media and the Rivers State Broadcasting Corporation. The inability of the government-owned media, like Radio Rivers Broadcasting Corporation to function effectively, its effect on the quality of service delivery, news coverage, staff welfare, and organizational setup, needs to be investigated.

Theoretical Framework

Institutional Theory

Institutional theory, as expounded by Meyer and Rowan (1977), focuses on how organizations conform to institutional pressures and norms within their environment. This theory suggests that public organizations are influenced by external institutional forces such as laws, regulations, and societal expectations. Institutional theorists assert that the institutional environment can strongly influence the development of formal structures in an organization, often more profoundly than market pressures. Meyer and Rowan (1977) argue that often these "institutional myths" are merely accepted ceremoniously in order for the organization to gain or maintain legitimacy in the institutional environment. Organizations adopt the "vocabularies of structure" prevalent in their environment such as specific job titles, procedures, and organizational roles. The adoption and prominent display of these institutionally-acceptable "trappings of legitimacy" help preserve an aura of organizational action based on "good faith". Legitimacy in the institutional environment helps ensure organizational survival. The theory

stressed that the net effect of institutional pressures is to increase the homogeneity of organizational structures in an institutional environment.

Assumptions of Institutional Theory

Institutional theory operates on several key assumptions that are essential for assessing the effects of staff recruitment and hiring procedures on service delivery in public organizations like Rivers State Television (RSTV) from 2010 to 2023. One primary assumption is that organizations are deeply influenced by their institutional environments, which consist of rules, norms, and cultural beliefs. These institutional pressures compel organizations to adopt certain structures and practices to gain legitimacy, stability, and survival. In the context of RSTV, this means that staff recruitment practices are not solely determined by internal managerial decisions but are also shaped by external expectations from governmental policies, societal norms, and professional standards. Another assumption of institutional theory is the concept of isomorphism, which suggests that organizations in similar environments tend to become more alike over time. This occurs through coercive isomorphism (pressure from regulatory bodies), mimetic isomorphism (emulating successful organizations), and normative isomorphism (influence from professional networks). For RSTV, this implies that its recruitment and hiring practices, such as recruitment, training, and performance evaluation, may mirror those of other public broadcasting entities to conform to industry standards and regulatory requirements. Understanding these isomorphic processes helps in assessing how recruitment and hiring practices at RSTV evolve in response to external pressures and how these practices affect service delivery. More so, institutional theory assumes that organizations seek to maintain legitimacy by adhering to accepted norms and practices. This pursuit of legitimacy often drives organizations to implement recruitment and hiring practices that are viewed as appropriate and effective by external stakeholders. For RSTV, maintaining legitimacy might involve adopting recruitment and hiring practices that promote transparency, fairness, and accountability. These practices can enhance employee motivation and performance, leading to improved service delivery. By assessing how RSTV aligns its recruitment and hiring practices with institutional norms over the 2010-2023 period, researchers can evaluate the impact of these practices on the organization's ability to deliver quality services to the public. The assumptions of institutional theory is relevant to Public organizations like Rivers State Television (RSTV) which is subject to various challenges and institutional pressures, including legal mandates, government regulations, and societal norms regarding transparency and accountability. Thus, recruitment and hiring practices within RSTV are shaped not only by internal organizational considerations but also by external institutional pressures. For example, RSTV may implement diversity and inclusion initiatives in response to societal expectations and government regulations. Furthermore, institutional theory highlights the importance of isomorphic processes, where organizations mimic each other's practices to gain legitimacy. In the context of recruitment and hiring at RSTV, this could manifest in the adoption of the practices observed in other public broadcasting corporations to conform to industry norms and gain legitimacy in the eyes of stakeholders.

Usefulness of Institutional Theory

Institutional theory provides a valuable framework for assessing the effect of recruitment and hiring on service delivery in public organizations like Rivers State Television (RSTV) from 2010 to 2023. This theory emphasized the role of institutions rules, norms, and routines as fundamental determinants of organizational behavior and performance. For instance, the formal rules governing hiring, training, and performance evaluation in RSTV are influenced by broader governmental policies and societal expectations, which can significantly affect the organization's ability to deliver high-quality services.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Human Resources Management

According to Amos et al. (2016), human resources management is the system of philosophies, policies, programs, practices and decisions that affect the attitudes, behaviour and performance of the people in an organisation so that they are satisfied and engaged, perform well and contribute to the organisation achieving its strategic objectives. The human resources management function comprises a group of unique activities such as carrying out a job analysis, drawing up a job description and carrying out a salary and wage survey to create a remuneration structure for an organisation. Typical human resources functions involve programs such as record keeping, recruiting, selection, training, employee relations, and compensation (Manroop, 2015). It stands to reason that these programs involve multiple activities such as transactional, traditional and transformational activities that provide a firm with a competitive advantage. These activities provide strategic value for the organisation only if their results are aligned to the strategic goals of the organisation. In terms of strategic human resource management, transformational activities are the activities that add value to the organisation, such as cultural or organisational change, structural realignment, strategic redirection, and increasing innovation and creativity (Thite, Kavanagh, and Johnson 2012). Kramar (2014) argued that the concept and processes of strategic human resources management (SHRM) helps to manage employees in a fast changing environment. Moreover, strategic human resource management explicitly linked people management policies and practices to the achievement of organisational outcomes and performance, most particularly financial and market outcome (Kramar 2014).

Recruitment and Hiring

Recruitment and hiring is perhaps the most popular role associated with human resource managers. It involves finding, reviewing credentials, screening, and selecting candidates for a company. An effective recruitment process results in the hiring of employees who are tailor-fit for the position and not just candidates who have the best credentials (Wright & Snell 2016). Recruitment and hiring practically involves the process of identifying, attracting, interviewing, selecting, and hiring and onboarding employees.

Employee Champion Role

Ulrich (1997) asserted that human resources management refers to the holistic management of employees and employee champion is one of the main functions of this discipline. This role has changed significantly in the public sector over the past two decades, especially for professionals (Brunetto and Beattie 2020). Advances in domestic and international labour laws highlight the prominence of employer-employee relationship management on the agenda of contemporary HR professionals. They are expected to cultivate new incentives to release the potential of knowledge workers, considered the major source of human capital in a knowledge economy (Gao et al 2016). Similarly, Neelankavil and Sengupta claimed that human capital is recognised as the most intangible asset a firm has to succeed in a highly competitive global environment. Employee champion also involves coaching and mentoring of employees as a way of offering full support to the employees for organisational competitiveness. Coaching focuses on the transfer and improvement of specific skillset over a short period of time, while mentoring extends to longer term development and nurturing required for overall leadership competencies (Schraeder & Jordan, 2011).

The Change Agent Role

As organisational changes are becoming common practice in management activities today, HR professionals are expected to assist organisations in keeping the employees committed and motivated throughout the change process (Kim and Egan, 2014). This is because when organisations undergo a change process, there is a great possibility that workers develop collective interpretation and views about the change initiatives in a way that management does not intend to endorse. Rumours and suspicions, combined with incomplete pieces of

information, may lead to unorthodox interpretations about the underlying purpose of the change initiatives (Isabella 1990 cited in Kim and Ryu 2011). Alizadeh, Dirani and Qiu (2020) suggested that the potential significance for HR in management of change can be viewed from a social constructionist perspective, focusing on discourse theory to explore the human resources management contribution in effecting language shifts during change as individuals construct their changing personal realities.

Concept of Service Delivery

Service delivery is a business framework that supplies services from a provider to a client. The service a business provides is something that the customer is unable to perform themselves, so there are a lot of elements to good service delivery. It encompasses all aspects of providing a service to a customer, including the initial interaction, onboarding, set up, conclusion of the service and follow-up provisions. Service delivery processes typically aim to provide the client with increased value by setting standards, policies, principles and constraints to guide all aspects of their business and customer interactions (Anyim, Ufodiana, & Olusanya, 2013). Sometimes service delivery may involve a third-party or outsourced supplier besides the provider and the client. Although services now account for between 60 and 80% of GDP and employment in many modern economies and despite a growing evidence of servicization in those economies (Machuca et al., 2007, Bettley et al., 2005; Cook et al., 2006; Howells, 2004), where organisations often attempt to increase revenues and the bottom line by integrating service activities and/or components into their traditional product offering, service operations management research remains worryingly meagre.

Components of Service Delivery

There are four logically sequenced steps or areas that organisations use to provide the best customer experience through their service delivery. Focusing on these elements can give a broader understanding of the scope of service delivery: **i. Service delivery**

Service delivery relates to the leadership principles, vision, mission, work habits and values of a service provider company (Wikipedia.com). Management controls these items, which set a basis for operations throughout the entire organization. Maintenance and development of these elements can develop the social processes of an organization and help serve the long-term success of the company.

Background of Rivers State Television (RSTV)

Rivers State Television, the pioneer television station of Rivers State Nigeria, came into existence on 31st December, 1974. Its initial take off location was Mgbuoba along Choba Road. The station transmitted under the headship of Mr. Gabriel Okara, the first General Manager of the Television Station. However, in 1976, there was a change in ownership of the station, as the federal government decided to take over all existing television stations in the country. By virtue of Decree No. 24 of 1977, Nigerian Television Authority (NTA) was charged with the responsibility of coordinating the activities of television stations across the country and following this development, the property of RSTV was taken over by NTA, Port Harcourt. In 1979, the Chief Melford Okilo civilian administration in Rivers State set up a committee to work out modalities and recommend the establishment of a state-owned television station. Under the supervision of Rivers State Broadcast Corporation (RSBC) alias Radio Rivers, Rivers State Television was resuscitated. In May, 1983, the station commenced test transmission of a one (1) kilowatt transmitter, and transmission lasted till 31st December, 1983 when the station went off-air, as a result of a Buhari led coup d'état which ousted the government of Alhaji Shehu Shagari. Consequently, a new Military Governor, Police Commissioner Fidelis Oyakhilome, was appointed to Rivers State. The new Governor ordered an inquiry into the circumstances that led to the closure of RSTV. Bases on the recommendations of the Committee, RSTV was reactivated and went on air under the supervision of Mr. Phillips

of Kings Engineering Limited, with the assistance of some RSBC engineering staff. On 28th June 1985, the Rivers State Government decided to establish a fullfledged television station. Mr. Comish Ekiye was then appointed the Acting General Manager of the station. On May 22, 1999, the station relocated to its permanent site at Elelewon, Port Harcourt, under the headship of Mrs. Florence Ekiye the General Manager. The statutory function of RSTV is to inform, educate and entertain their audience while stimulating and promoting the desired political, social and economic awareness, promoting national consciousness, civic responsibility and the inculcation of the spirit of tolerance and variegated shades of opinion. In this vein, Rivers State Television (RSTV) disseminates government policies and programmes to the people.

Organisational Structure of RSTV

At the topmost of the management hierarchy of RSTV is the General Manager. He is the person that oversees the overall operations of the Station and it is his duty to ensure that the station’s operations remain viable and productive. Also among the top management staff in RSTV are the Director of Internal Audit and the Secretary of the organisation.

Figure 2.1: Organisational Structure of RSTV

Source: Office Desk, Rivers State Television, (2023)

Beyond the Topmost management, RSTV is equally divided into Eight (8) departmental Units. Each of the departments is headed by a Director, who oversees the operations of the department he heads, and every staff in the department is answerable to the director. The departmental units are further exanciated below:

Departmental Structure of RSTV

i. Engineering Department

This department oversees the technical operations of the station and ensures that the station is always on-air as at when due. They also see to the full functionality of all the broadcast equipment that is required for the successful operations of the station. The engineering department is in charge of maintaining the transmission room (TS room) which houses the transmitters that send the television signals that are received by the viewers at home. The engineering department is headed by the Director of Engineering. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy in the engineering department, is the Deputy Director. Unlike other departments whose 3rd in command are called managers, the third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Chief Engineer, who is followed by the Assistant Chief Engineer. Other staff members include; Principal Engineer, Principal Technical Officer, Senior Engineer, Senior Technical Officer, Engineer I, Techincal Officer I, Engineer II and Technical Officer II.

ii. Programmes Department

This is the brain behind the contents aired for the viewer’s delight. The programmes department, conceptualises ideas and turns them into different programmes, they also handle the design of the programme schedules and allot slots to the different programmes that are aired on the station. The programmes department is headed by the Director of Programmes. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy in the programmes department, is the Deputy Director. The third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Manager Programmes. Other staff members include; Controller Programmes, Controller Production Service, Principal Producer, Principal Presenter, Principal Designer, Principal Librarian, Senior Cameraman, Senior Presenter, Senior Producer, Senior Designer, Senior Librarian and Producer 1, Presenter 1, Graphics Officer, Presenter 2.

iii. Commercial Services Department

This department is foisted with the responsibility of churning in revenue for the station, in terms of seeking and procuring advertisements, and other such revenue earning activities. The commercial department is headed by the Director of Commercial Services. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy, is the Deputy Director of Commercial Services. The third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Manager Commercial Services. Other staff members include; Controller Commercial Services, Principal Commercial Officer, Principal Presenter, Senior Commercial Officer, Commercial Officer 1, Commercial Officer 2 and Traffic Officer.

iv. Finance/Accounts Department

This is the department than handles the financial management of the station. They are responsible for the collection and disbursement of funds needed to keep the station running. They also make sure that all the revenue accruable to the station is collected and accounted for. The commercial department is headed by the Director of Finance/Accounts. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy, is the Deputy Director of Finance/Accounts. The third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Manager Finance/Accounts. Other staff members include; Controller Finance/Accounts, Principal Accountant, Senior Accountant, Senior Research, Accounts Officer 1 and Accounts Officer 2.

v. News Department

The News department is manned by seasoned journalist, who source and sorts through news worthy events to be aired on the station. The department ensures that news are being read as at when due according to the programme schedule of the station, and also make sure that the news has been properly edited to eliminate any material that ought not to be in the news. The news department is headed by the Director of News. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy, is the Deputy Director of News. The third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Manager News. Other staff members include; Controller News, Principal Presenter, Principal Editor, Principal Translator, Senior News Presenter, Senior Editor, Senior Translator, News Presenter 1, Editor 1, Translator 1, News Presenter 2, Editor 2 and Translator2.

vi. Current Affairs Department

Formerly a part of the News department, the current affairs department as the name implies is charged with keeping the station abreast with current affairs. The current affairs department is headed by the Director of Current Affairs. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy, is the Deputy Director of Current Affairs. The third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Manager Current Affairs. Other staff members include; Controller Current Affairs, Principal reporter, Senior Reporter, Reporter 1 and Reporter 2.

vii. Research, Planning & Statistics Department

The department of Research Planning & Statistics monitors and evaluates the Station to make sure that the station is achieving its set objective. It carries out periodic assessment of audience perception of the station's schedule of programmes, and the result gotten from the audience research is the basis upon which the areas of programme focus is determined for the purpose of future broadcasts. The department also ensures that the programme planning committee keeps up with the guidelines of broadcasting and fair allotment of programmes as outlined in the National Broadcasting Commission code. This department is headed by the Director of Research, Planning and Statistics. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy, is the Deputy Director of Research, Planning and Statistics. The third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Manager Research, Planning and Statistics. Other staff members include; Controller Research, Planning and Statistics, Principal Research, Planning and Statistics, Senior Research, Planning and Statistics, Researcher 1 and Researcher 2.

viii. Administrative Department

This department oversees the administration of the station, the department coordinates the activities of the various other department, handles personnel relations among other administrative functions. The Administration department is headed by the Director of Administration. The next in line in the order of staff hierarchy, is the Deputy Director of Administration. The third person in the order of staff hierarchy is the Manager Administration. Other staff members include; Controller Administration, Chief Personnel Officer, Principal Admin Officer, Senior Admin Officer, Admin officer 1, Admin Officer 2.

Method

This study employed the survey research design. Based on the information obtained from the office of the Director of Administration, RSTV (2022); there are eight departments within the organizational structure of RSTV with top level staff of 12 within the Engineering Department, 18 for Programmes Department, 25 for Commercial Services Department, 8 within the Finance/Accounts Department, 16 for News Department, 8 for Current Affairs Department, Research, 11 within the Planning & Statistics Department and 17 within the Administrative Department. Therefore, there are 115 staff of Rivers State Television designated for this study. **Table 1:**

Population of the Study

S/N	Department	Total
1	Programmes	18
2	Engineering	12
3	Commercial	25
4	Finance/ Accounts	8
5	News	16
6	Current Affairs	8
7	Research, Planning and Statistics	11
8	Administrative	17
	TOTAL	115

Source: Office of the Director Administration, RSTV (2023).

The sample size was determined using the sample size determination formula of Taro Yamene at 0.05 level of significance (Baridam, 2001). Formula: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

Where:

n = sample size N = Population size

e = Level of significance desired

Substituting;

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \frac{115}{1 + 115(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{115}{1 + 0.2875} \\
 &= \frac{115}{1.2875} = 89
 \end{aligned}$$

The sample size therefore is 89 respondents

Primary data was obtained through structured questionnaire. Secondary source of data for the study included official publications of the Rivers State Television and news reports. Others include textbooks, relevant articles, journals, newspapers.

The study employed a four point type rating scale (Ordinal 4-point Likert Scale) with the response mode of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 respectively.

The simple percentage method of analysis was adopted for data analysis while the hypothesis was tested with the Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient using T- test.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion

Eighty nine (89) copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents as indicated in the sample size. The result of the questionnaire (survey) distributed and retrieved is shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Analysis of Rate of Questionnaire Response

Questionnaire	Respondents	Percentage Returned (%)
Total distributed	89	100.00
Returned	80	89.88 (Valid)

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 above showed that a total of 89 research questionnaire were distributed and 80 copies were filled and returned which yielded 89.88% return of the questionnaire. This was used to make valid deductions and conclusions.

Table 3: Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 – 25	9	11
26 – 35	46	57
36 – 45	10	13
46 – 55	15	19
Total	80	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 presented the age distribution of respondents. The results showed that 9 out of the 80 respondents are in the age bracket of 18-25, representing 19%; 46 representing 57% are in the age of 26-35, while 10 representing 13% are in the age range of 36-45 and 15 respondents representing only 11% of the respondents are aged between 46-55. This implies that 57% of the respondents are over 25 years of age.

Table 4: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percent
OND/ND	2	3
BSC/B.ED/B.TECH	52	65
MSC/MBA/M.TECH	18	22
DR./Ph.D	8	10
Total	80	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

Table 4 above showed that out of the total 80 respondents 3(3%) have Ordinary National Diploma or National Diploma (OND/ND), 52(65%) have Bachelors' Degree (BSC/B.ED/B.TECH), 18(22%) have Masters Degree and 8(10%) have Doctorate Degree. This results implied that 52(65%) of the total respondents university graduate. How do Staff recruitment and hiring procedures and hiring procedures affect service quality at Rivers State Television?

NO.	Cluster	A:	How do	Staff SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Sd
recruitment and hiring procedures and hiring procedures affect service quality at Rivers State Television?									
1	You are pleased with the level of clarity and transparency of the job descriptions provided during the recruitment process in your organisation.	55		15	9	1		3.55	0.74
2	Recruitment process accurately represent the organization's culture and values at the Rivers State Television.	52		20	5	3		3.52	0.78
3	In your opinion, the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the Staff recruitment and hiring procedures and hiring procedures at the Rivers State Television is satisfactory.	58		17	5	0		3.67	0.59
4	There are aspects of the recruitment process you found particularly challenging or confusing in your job areas.	35		15	20	10		2.94	1.09
5	You are particularly satisfied with the Communication and feedback received throughout the recruitment process.	40		22	10	8		3.51	1.77

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 5 reveals that items 1-5 have mean and standard deviation as follows 3.55(0.74) 3.52 (0.78) 3.67(0.59), 2.94(1.09) indicating strongly agree.

Test of Hypothesis

The test of hypotheses was carried out using T-test with the aid of Spearman Rank Order Coefficient Correlation using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Ho: Staff recruitment and hiring procedures and hiring procedures do not significantly affect service quality at the Rivers State Television.

Table 6: T-test Analyses of the effect of Staff Recruitment and Hiring Procedures on Service Quality at the Rivers State Television.

Hypothesis	N	X	SD	t-cal	tcritical value	Level of sign	df	Decision
H01	80	3.41	1.04	1.17	3.245	0.001	80	Reject

Source: Research Output, 2024

Table 6: presents the T-test statistical analysis of the effect of Staff recruitment and hiring procedures on service quality at the Rivers State Television. The T- calculated value is 1.17 at 80 degree of freedom (df) and 0.001 level of significance. The T-statistic is 3.245, indicating that there is a statistically positive significant difference between the groups. The p-value is 0.001, which is less than the critical level (e.g., 0.05), led to rejecting the null hypothesis (H0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H1). This suggests that Staff recruitment and hiring procedures had significant effect on quality of service delivery at the Rivers State Television.

Discussion

Staff Recruitment and Hiring Procedures and Service Quality

The test of hypothesis (T-test) in table 6 revealed that T-statistic (3.245) is positive indicating that there is a statistically positive relationship between Staff recruitment and hiring procedures on the quality of service delivery. The p-value is 0.001 suggests that Staff recruitment and hiring procedures had significant effect on service quality at the Rivers State Television. The result of this hypothesis validates the opinion of Okeke, Onyishi, and Ugwu (2019) study on HRM practices in Nigerian universities. The study highlighted the importance of HRM in recruiting and retaining qualified academic staff, which directly impacted the quality of education and research outputs. This empirical evidence underscores how recruitment and hiring practices in the public sector contribute to improved services delivery. The finding of this study is equally in consonance with a study by Butler, Minbaeva, Maleka, Maloney, Nardon, Paunova and Zimmermann (2018) on the HRM implications of global teams for international organisations in which they found that HRM has an important function in the management of global teams in three essential ways. They noted that HRM has a crucial role in the recruiting and training of team members with the required skills and characteristics that facilitate leveraging diversity, such as intercultural communication, intercultural learning and managing emotions and identities.

Conclusion/Recommendations

The study has empirically addressed the significant effect of recruitment and hiring practices on service delivery at Rivers State Television (RSTV) between 2010 to 2023. The practices of recruitment and hiring procedures at Rivers State Television (RSTV) illuminates its impact on service delivery within public organizations. Through effective Staff recruitment and hiring procedures practices, RSTV can attract onboard talented individuals, ensuring the organization possesses the requisite skills and expertise to fulfill its mission. By employing a comprehensive human resource management framework, RSTV can align its HR strategies and with its overarching goals, fostering a culture of excellence and accountability among its workforce.

This study suggests the following recommendations:

- i. Recruitment heads should utilize modern recruitment techniques and implement a strategic recruitment plan that focuses on attracting diverse talent pools to meet the specific needs of not only RSTV but also that of the general public;
- ii. The River State Broadcasting Corporation as well as the management of Rivers State Television Authority should invest in continuous learning opportunities, including workshops, seminars, and online courses, to enhance the capabilities of RSTV's workforce on recruitment practices and hiring procedures.

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